
152. M dwarfs and the Jao gap

IN ESSAY #42, I described a number of new features in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram of nearby stars, based on the Gaia DR2 study by Babusiaux et al. (2018).

One of these was a very narrow (~ 0.05 mag) gap in the M dwarf lower main sequence, first reported in the Gaia DR2 data by Jao et al. (2018). It confirms a similar feature hinted at in infrared data from 2MASS, and is confirmed in the EDR3 Gaia Catalogue of Nearby Stars, 330 000 objects within 100 pc (Smart et al. 2021, Fig. 17).

The gap is near the luminosity–temperature region where M dwarfs transition from partially to fully convective, near spectral type M3.0V at around $0.35M_{\odot}$: lower mass dwarfs have fully convective interiors, while more massive stars (including the Sun) have convective envelopes surrounding a radiative zone, a denser region where convective motions are suppressed.

Jao et al. (2018) suggested that the gap is related to a subtle change in structure (decrease in radius) at the transition region, and it has since been widely referred to as the ‘Jao gap’. In this essay, I will look at some more details of this interesting feature, and its implications.

A THEORETICAL EXPLANATION was soon forthcoming, and one seemingly consistent with existing models (MacDonald & Gizis, 2018). Qualitatively, they argued, the gap arises because core convection in low-mass stars helps mix the intermediate nuclear fusion products, allowing the star to fuse H more efficiently. They showed that the mixing of ${}^3\text{He}$ during the merger of the envelope and core convection zones occurs over a narrow range of masses. This implies an associated dip in the luminosity function, which is then responsible for the gap.

WHILE CONFIRMING that nuclear burning and mixing of ${}^3\text{He}$ provide an overall explanation, Baraffe & Chabrier (2018) drew attention to two crucial features of their own models. The first is the expansion of stars with $M \gtrsim 0.34M_{\odot}$, due to the fast increase of central ${}^3\text{He}$ abundance, causing a rapid increase of nuclear energy production (and in contrast to fully convective models with $M \lesssim 0.33M_{\odot}$, which evolve at essentially constant radius during the first Gyr).

The second is the significant decrease in radius during the episodic event of convective core/envelope merging, which only concerns the narrow mass range $0.34 - 0.36M_{\odot}$. Together, the merging of the convective core with the envelope results in a *decrease* of ${}^3\text{He}$ abundance in the centre, and thus a decrease in luminosity.

THE EXPLANATION for this gap in terms of the non-equilibrium burning and mixing of ${}^3\text{He}$ in the stellar core, and consistent with the expected transition from partially to fully convective interiors in M dwarfs, was predicted by van Saders & Pinsonneault (2012), who termed it the ‘convective kissing instability’.

A nice summary has been given by Silverstein et al. (2022): Core ${}^3\text{He}$ fusion leads to the development of a convective core that grows and eventually merges with the convective outer envelope. Convective mixing then transports ${}^3\text{He}$ away from the core, reducing the nuclear reaction rate and causing the core to contract and again separate from the convective envelope. This leads to the emergence of a ${}^3\text{He}$ burning instability where the core undergoes damped, periodic transitions between partial and full convection until a balance is achieved in the ${}^3\text{He}$ abundance and the star remains fully convective.

This transitory phase in core energy transport leads to small, slowly varying oscillations in radius and luminosity in a narrow mass range, $0.34 - 0.37M_{\odot}$. It is then characterised by the observed gap, being a deficit of stars, in the HR diagram.

The kissing instability is possibly manifest in the structure of the Hyades main sequence (essay #150), suggested as a possible cause of the increased scatter for masses below $\sim 0.35M_{\odot}$ (Brandner et al., 2023).

THE DISCOVERY of the gap, and the appreciation that it represents a powerful tool for testing the physics of M dwarfs, has motivated a number of subsequent theoretical and modelling studies (e.g. Feiden et al. 2021; Mansfield & Kroupa 2021; Boudreaux & Chaboyer 2023).

Detailed modelling by Mansfield & Kroupa (2023), suggests that the phenomenon may lead to a decrease in width of the main sequence over time, and a change in its slope, which may in turn offer prospects for its use in age-dating for single stars and stellar populations.

FOURIER ANALYSIS of the HR diagram, using 1.16 million stars within 200 pc from Gaia DR2, has revealed further structural features (Jao & Feiden, 2020).

They showed, for example, that there are more stars above the gap than below it, implying that stars spend more time above the gap while subject to variability associated with the ^3He instability.

The width of the gap depends on colour up to $G_{BP} - G_{RP} = 2.7$, beyond which the gap is hardly seen. A new low-density region is centred at $M_G = 10.7$ mag and $G_{BP} - G_{RP} = 2.8$. The main sequence also appears to have fine stripes where the stellar densities vary compared to adjacent regions on the main sequence.

They attribute these various structural features to the complexities of the atmospheric features and opacities over this specific mass range.

VARIOUS OBSERVATIONS have been made to establish the physical properties of stars in this mass range, and to explore the associated model predictions.

Rabus et al. (2019) reported 13 new stellar diameters for low-mass dwarfs obtained with VLTI-PIONIER. Together with accurate Gaia DR2 parallaxes, they yield precise radii, temperatures, masses, and luminosities. Amongst their findings, they identified a discontinuity in the T_{eff} -radius plane, at around $0.23M_{\odot}$, which they also attribute to the transition from the partially- to fully-convective regime, although slightly below the Jao gap.

Dieterich et al. (2021) used HST-STIS spectroscopy of 10 M dwarfs in five closely separated binary systems over the mass range $0.083 - 0.405M_{\odot}$, i.e. spanning the location of the gap. They compared their derived parameters (temperature, radius, luminosity, etc.) with five different evolutionary models (Dartmouth, MESA/MIST, Baraffe–Chabrier, PARSEC, and YAPSI), but finding only marginal agreement with evolutionary models.

STELLAR ACTIVITY is another phenomenon of interest for stars in this mass range, and for which the dynamos of partially and fully convective stars may be fundamentally different (e.g. Lu et al., 2023).

The possibility that a transition between dynamo modes also occurs at the transition to complete convection was considered by Houdebine et al. (2017). Mullan & Houdebine (2020) combined Ca II data with projected rotational velocities to examine the correlations between rotation and activity in K–M dwarfs. They found that such a transition appears to be close to, but earlier than, the Jao gap, and probably related to the existence of a small convective core.

From a survey of the activity of 480 M dwarfs, Jao et al. (2023) found that M dwarfs with H α in emission are almost entirely located 0–0.5 mag above the top edge of the gap in the HR diagram, while no stars in or below the gap show emission. They argue that their results suggest that the most massive fully-convective stars lose their angular momentum faster than both partially convective stars and less massive fully-convective stars.

Baraffe & Chabrier (2018) also noted that the gap could impact the field of cataclysmic variable, by affecting the evolution of low-mass donors, and perhaps offering an explanation for the ‘CV period gap’, viz. the dearth of systems in the period range 2–3 h (essay #140).

THE EXOPLANET system TOI-696 (LHS 1678) has recently received some attention as a consequence of the host star being situated within this gap. It consists of two Earth-mass ($0.35M_{\oplus}$ and $1.4M_{\oplus}$) transiting planets, and a likely brown dwarf, orbiting a bright ($V = 12.5$ mag) M2 dwarf at 19.9 pc (Silverstein et al., 2022).

The host star is the only TESS systems residing in the gap, although TOI-5205 is very close (Kanodia et al., 2023). It may therefore be part of a stellar population that has transitioned from being partially to fully convective, exhibiting long-term radial pulsations as they migrate back and forth across the gap over the course of billions of years. Any effect of the associated stellar astrophysics on exoplanet evolution is currently unknown.

IT IS STILL early days in our understanding of the gap. As Baraffe & Chabrier (2018) wrote: ‘*Just a small gap in a colour–magnitude diagram could provide a deep insight into the interior structure of low-mass stars.*’